

Understanding Human Factors in Aircraft Avionics Operations

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Abstract

The Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) Extension, Safety, and Security Act of 2016, specifically Section 2102 on Cockpit Automation Management, requires aircraft companies to ensure that air carrier training programs incorporate training for pilots to monitor automation systems and control the flight path without using autopilot or auto flight systems. The Act also mandates the development of measurable metrics to evaluate pilot monitoring proficiency, offers guidance for aviation safety inspectors in assessing pilots' manual flight skills, and provides standards for enhanced pilot training as defined in the November 12, 2013, Federal Register final rule. This research explores the complexities of human factors in operating aircraft with avionics, focusing on the experiences and challenges aviation students encounter. Against a regulatory backdrop and the prevalence of advanced avionic systems, the study investigates avionics training effectiveness, operational challenges, human-technology interactions, the necessity of ongoing training, and safety risk mitigation. Through a qualitative approach, data was collected from interviews with aviation students, highlighting the critical need for rigorous training, effective human-technology interaction, continuous skill enhancement, and comprehensive safety measures in aviation operations.

Keywords: *avionics, human factors, aircraft operation*

Introduction

The Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) Extension, Safety, and Security Act of 2016, specifically Section 2102 on Cockpit Automation Management, mandates aircraft companies to implement verification processes for air carrier training programs that include pilot training in monitoring automation systems and controlling flight paths without autopilot or auto flight systems. The Act also requires air carriers to establish measurable metrics to evaluate pilot monitoring skills, offers guidance for aviation safety inspectors to assess pilot proficiency in manual flight, and provides compliance standards for enhanced pilot training, as detailed in the Federal Register on November 12, 2013.

The program offered to aviation students includes courses designed to equip them thoroughly in aviation, incorporating general education, aircraft maintenance, and research. Among these is the Basic Aircraft Instruments course, which prepares students to understand avionic systems as they relate to flight instruments. Avionics, or any aircraft system dependent on electronics, plays a critical role in training future pilots.

Despite advancements in avionics, human factors remain central to safe aircraft operation. According to Johnston (2021), understanding how crew members interact with their environment is essential to developing effective avionics, both in the cockpit and throughout the aircraft. Recent incidents, such as aviation accidents in the Philippines where two passengers died in a Cessna training flight (Philstar.com, 2023), underscore the significance of human factors. Studies indicate that over 88% of general aviation accidents result from human error, often due to loss of control during flight (Winingham, 2022).

This research aims to explore the underlying challenges and gaps in human factors impacting aircraft operation with avionics, with the objective of proposing an action plan to address these issues.

Research Question/ Objectives

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of aviation students in operating aircraft with avionics?
2. What challenges are encountered in operating aircraft with avionics?

3. What strategies can be explored to address the challenges faced by captains operating aircraft with avionics?

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative methodology to gather data. Various qualitative tools were used, including in-depth interviews, focused observations, recordings, and detailed notes, as described by Girardin (2023). This approach aimed to provide insights and an understanding of the participants' lived experiences by analyzing social dynamics and human behavior. Below is a summary of the research design, setting, participant selection, data collection procedures, data analysis methods, trustworthiness measures, researcher reflexivity, and instruments used.

Research Design

A single-case study design was applied in this research. Yin (2003) suggests that case study designs are useful when: (a) the research aims to answer "how" and "why" questions, (b) the behavior of participants cannot be manipulated, (c) the researcher wants to cover contextual conditions they believe are relevant to the phenomenon, or (d) the boundaries between the phenomenon and context are unclear.

Participants/Respondents

The study targeted eight aviation students selected through purposive sampling. Recommendations were obtained from authorized personnel to identify students who met the following criteria: (a) 3rd or 4th-year students, (b) 3 to 5 years of experience flying aircraft equipped with avionics, and (c) proficiency in English.

Instruments

A self-designed interview guide was used to gather relevant information. Participant responses were recorded and documented through audio recordings and note-taking tools. These data-collecting instruments, including interviews and document analysis, enabled a comprehensive understanding of the aviation students' experiences, challenges, and problem-solving approaches in operating aircraft with avionics.

Procedure

This study followed data collection methods outlined by John Creswell, which included: (1) Selecting cases that met predefined criteria, (2) Obtaining permissions from relevant authorities, (3) Contacting participants and informing them of confidentiality and anonymity rights, (4) Beginning data collection promptly, (5) Documenting interviews thoroughly, (6) Reviewing field notes with participants for validation, and (7) Coding and organizing data systematically. All interviews were conducted in person on campus, and strict confidentiality measures were observed, including obtaining written consent before recording.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data analysis in this study aimed to uncover the insights within non-numerical data such as interview responses, open-ended survey answers, and observations (Dye, 2023). It sought to understand the reasons behind participants' behaviors and experiences. The analysis followed Dodge's (2011) steps: (1) Organizing and preparing data with transcriptions in Microsoft Word, (2) Reflecting on data through close reading, (3) Initial coding by sorting responses and documenting key ideas, (4) Refining codes and defining thematic categories, (5) Constructing a narrative linking themes to passages, and (6) Interpreting meaning to derive deeper insights from the data.

Results

After analyzing interview transcripts, the researchers identified five key themes related to human factors in aviation: Avionics Training Effectiveness, Operational Challenges, Human-Technology Interaction, Continuous Training Needs, and Safety Risk Mitigation. Below is a synthesis of the participants' narratives on each theme.

Theme 1: Avionics Training Effectiveness

Avionics training effectiveness remains crucial, as pilots must thoroughly understand advanced technological systems to ensure safe operations. If avionics training is insufficient, pilots may encounter challenges in applying critical decision-making skills during actual flights. The effectiveness of training programs in equipping pilots with practical knowledge and operational readiness is central to the theme of avionics training. This importance was underscored by several participants:

Key informant 1 shared:

"Advanced avionics systems make our flight management easier due to fast results given by the specific instrument."

Key informant 2 noted:

"Stay calm and identify the faulty avionics switches and commend procedures if necessary."

Key informant 3 observed:

"Advancements in instrument displays made it quite easier for us pilots to operate in our flights since most of the information that we

need such as ground speed, altitude, heading, etc. is already shown on just one screen, and these modern instrument displays have become more reliable than analog displays, especially in IMC conditions."

Theme 2: Operational Challenges

Operational challenges in avionics influence pilots' daily tasks and bear direct implications for flight safety and efficiency. Recognizing these challenges enables the development of practical solutions for issues encountered when interacting with complex avionics systems. Key statements from participants reflect various experiences with operational difficulties:

Key informant 1 explained:

"In a recent flight, we encountered an issue with the primary navigation display. Following established procedures, we switched to the backup system, cross-checked the information, and coordinated with air traffic control. The redundancy in the system and adherence to procedures allowed us to complete the flight with minimal disruption safely."

Key informant 3 stated:

"The only challenge that I have experienced so far is learning how to operate these high-tech displays."

According to Avionics-Safety Overcoming the Future Aviation Challenges Through Viable Safety Solutions (2019), aviation safety management prioritizes flight safety, integrating safety components through systematic management.

Theme 3: Human-Technology Interaction

The interaction between pilots and avionics systems is fundamental, impacting pilots' ability to effectively interpret and respond to system data. A deep understanding of human factors in this interaction is essential for successful operations. Participants reflected on this interplay and shared insights:

Key informant 2 observed:

"Advancement in aircraft avionic systems makes our decision-making and workload less efficient because of the efficiency, stability, and information we need internally and externally during flight."

Key informant 5 remarked:

"Through practice and simulation."

Human-Computer Interaction on the Modern Flight Deck (2021) states that new technology in avionics, such as electronic flight bags and automated controls, enhances pilots' situational awareness, decision-making, and communication abilities, supporting complex flight tasks.

Theme 4: Continuous Training Needs

Continuous training is essential as avionic technologies rapidly evolve, requiring pilots to stay updated with advancements to maintain operational safety. The need for ongoing education in response to technological changes is vital in aviation. Participants highlighted various aspects of this theme:

Key informant 1 shared:

"In a way, we're still trained for certain problems like this (flapless landing)."

Key informant 3 emphasized:

"Integrating training regarding the advancements of technologies can be a big boost for pilots and can reduce the workload for flight instructors during actual flights since, with the proper training in ground school, student pilots can gain a basic idea already on how to operate these new advancements."

Understanding the Importance of Recurrent Training for Pilots (2023) asserts that continuous training allows pilots to remain current with regulatory, procedural, and technological changes, thereby enhancing safety practices.

Theme 5: Safety Risk Mitigation

Safety risk mitigation is a high priority in aviation, as reliance on advanced avionics introduces vulnerabilities that can impact flight safety. Recognizing failure points and implementing effective risk management strategies is crucial for safe flight operations. Key informants expressed concerns regarding risk factors and mitigation:

Key informant 1 stated:

"In a recent flight, we encountered an issue with the primary navigation display. Following established procedures, we switched to the backup system, cross-checked the information, and coordinated with air traffic control. The redundancy in the system and adherence to procedures allowed us to complete the flight with minimal disruption safely."

Key informant 3 observed:

"Since most of the modern aircraft's instruments have been upgraded to high-tech digital displays, faulty avionics can cause the modern instruments to fail and also provide false information to the pilots, thus, adding more workload towards the pilots in flight and compromising the safety of the flight."

The Aviation Instructor's Handbook (2020) explains that effective risk management proactively identifies hazards and mitigates risks, enhancing decision-making practices to minimize the inherent risks in flight operations.

Conclusion

Based on the study findings and the insights from the eight participants, the following conclusions were drawn:

The research focused on examining human factors in the use of avionics in aircraft operations. It delved into five critical themes: Avionics Training Effectiveness, Operational Challenges, Human-Technology Interaction, Continuous Training Needs, and Safety Risk Mitigation, aiming to better understand the complex relationship between pilots and avionics systems. The study's value lies in highlighting the importance of effective training, intuitive system interfaces, ongoing skill enhancement, and robust safety measures in aviation. From these insights, practical recommendations emerged, proposing improvements in training programs, interface usability, skill development, and safety protocols—all with potential benefits for aviation efficiency and safety.

While comprehensive, the study recognizes limitations, particularly the subjective perspectives of participants and possible gaps in capturing broader human factors. For future research, suggestions include designing specialized training approaches, developing advanced interface technology, conducting longitudinal studies on the effects of continuous training, and creating innovative safety strategies. Ultimately, this study provides a thorough basis for understanding human factors in aviation avionics, offering actionable guidance for industry advancements and further research.

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